

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**CONTINUED ADVANCEMENTS IN TREATMENT
PROTOCOLS, VACCINATION EFFORTS, AND
UNDERSTANDING LONG COVID-19.****Aziza Abdullah Alabdullatif¹, Eman Salman Alsafwani¹, Fatimah Mohammed Al-Hay¹,
Khadija Ali Alkhamis²**¹ Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal Hospital - National Guard – Dammam – Saudi Arabia² National Guard Hospital - Riyadh - Saudi Arabia**Abstract:**

Background: *Advancements in treatment protocols, vaccination efforts, and understanding of long COVID have been pivotal in addressing the ongoing challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. Long COVID, characterized by persistent symptoms following SARS-CoV-2 infection, has emerged as a significant public health concern. Research has focused on understanding its epidemiology, pathophysiology, and potential interventions.*

Aim: *This overview explores the advancements in treatment protocols, vaccination, and long-term care of COVID-19*

Methods: *This comprehensive review uses PUBMED and Google Scholar as primary databases for articles collected until March 2021.*

Conclusion: *The COVID-19 pandemic, stemming from zoonotic transmission in Wuhan, has become a major global health crisis highlighting the need for international collaboration in health management. Progress in treatments and vaccination efforts, while significant, requires continued commitment to address challenges and enhance support for those affected by the virus and its long-term impacts.*

Keywords: *Covid – Treatment – long term care.*

Corresponding author:**Aziza Abdullah Alabdullatif**

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Please cite this article in press Aziza Abdullah Alabdullatif et al, *Continued Advancements In Treatment Protocols, Vaccination Efforts, And Understanding Long Covid-19*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2021; 08(9).

INTRODUCTION:

The COVID-19 pandemic, caused by the novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, has profoundly impacted global health and society since its emergence in late 2019. Initially identified in Wuhan, China, the virus was linked to live animal wet markets, where zoonotic transmission likely occurred, allowing the virus to cross from animals, such as bats and pangolins, to humans. This zoonotic nature of coronaviruses is crucial for understanding the origins of COVID-19, as it highlights the environmental and social factors that facilitated the outbreak. (1) On January 30, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared COVID-19 a Public Health Emergency of International Concern, emphasizing the global significance of the outbreak. As the virus spread rapidly, the WHO officially classified it as a pandemic on March 11, 2020, following a surge in cases that exceeded 118,000 across more than 110 countries. (2) This declaration underscored the urgent need for coordinated international responses to manage the crisis effectively. The pandemic has been characterized by conflicting messages from various media and health officials, leading to widespread confusion and anxiety among the public. The rapid spread of misinformation, coupled with inconsistent public health measures across different nations, has complicated efforts to control the virus's transmission. (3) Healthcare professionals worldwide have been mobilized to address the crisis, drawing on their training to manage health emergencies effectively. Healthcare professionals worldwide have been mobilized to address the crisis, drawing on their training to manage health emergencies effectively. (2) COVID-19 is part of a larger family of coronaviruses, which can cause illnesses ranging from mild respiratory infections to severe diseases like Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS). The pandemic has not only highlighted the vulnerabilities in global health systems but also the interconnectedness of human and animal health, emphasizing the need for a One Health approach to prevent future outbreaks. (1)

Advancements in Treatment Protocols

The treatment protocols for COVID-19 have evolved significantly since the onset of the pandemic, driven by ongoing research and clinical findings. The National Institutes of Health (NIH) has played a pivotal role in developing and updating COVID-19 Treatment Guidelines, regularly revised to reflect the

latest evidence and recommendations for managing the disease. (4, 5) These guidelines encompass a range of therapeutic options tailored to different patient populations, including hospitalized patients and those with mild to moderate symptoms. Remdesivir has emerged as a key antiviral option for hospitalized patients, particularly effective when administered early in the disease course, leading to faster recovery times. This medication is particularly beneficial for those at high risk of progressing to severe disease, highlighting the importance of early intervention in treatment protocols. (6) In addition to antiviral therapies, immunomodulatory treatments have gained attention, especially for patients experiencing severe inflammation during later stages of the disease. These therapies aim to modulate the immune response, which can be critical in preventing severe respiratory distress. Clinical trials have demonstrated that timely administration of immunomodulatory drugs can mitigate disease severity and reduce hospital stays. (7, 8) Furthermore, the integration of antithrombotic therapy has been recognized as essential for managing thrombotic complications in COVID-19 patients, particularly those at high risk. (8, 9)

Vaccination Efforts and Developments

The global vaccination efforts against COVID-19 have been unprecedented, driven by the urgent need to control a pandemic that has caused immense morbidity and mortality worldwide. Approximately 90 institutions are developing COVID-19 vaccines, which are crucial for high-risk groups and mass immunization strategies to achieve herd immunity and prevent future outbreaks. (10, 11) Emergency Use Authorization (EUA) facilitates the rapid advancement of vaccine candidates, a regulatory mechanism that allows for expedited approval during public health emergencies, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. (12, 13) The efficacy of these vaccines has been a focal point of research, with many demonstrating significant effectiveness in preventing severe disease and hospitalization. (14) The development process has involved various platforms, primarily targeting the virus's spike (S) protein, which is essential for eliciting an immune response. (15) As vaccines have been rolled out globally, the public health impact has been substantial, leading to a marked reduction in illness and deaths associated with COVID-19. However, the success of vaccination campaigns is not solely dependent on the availability of vaccines; it also hinges on public acceptance.

Vaccine hesitancy, driven by misinformation and distrust in health systems, poses a significant challenge to achieving widespread vaccination coverage. (12) Efforts to promote vaccine acceptance through community engagement and education are critical to overcoming these barriers. (16, 17) Logistical challenges in the vaccine supply chain have also been a concern, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where access to vaccines is limited. Strategies for global vaccine distribution must address these challenges to ensure equitable access for all populations. Furthermore, substantial funding from governments and organizations has been pivotal in supporting the research and development of COVID-19 vaccines, enabling rapid progress in vaccine technology and deployment.

Understanding Long COVID

Long COVID, also known as COVID long-haulers, refers to the persistence of symptoms or the emergence of new symptoms related to SARS-CoV-2 infection for more than 28 days after diagnosis. This condition has become a significant health issue, affecting a substantial portion of the population globally and presenting challenges for health systems. The symptoms of Long COVID are notably heterogeneous, often impacting multiple organ systems, which necessitates a holistic management approach to address the diverse experiences of patients. (18) Individuals suffering from Long COVID frequently report ongoing symptoms that can affect at least three organ systems, with common manifestations including fatigue, shortness of breath, cognitive dysfunction, and various neurological issues. (19, 20) The complexity of these symptoms complicates treatment, as they can fluctuate in intensity and may overlap with other health conditions, making it essential to tailor management strategies to individual patient needs. (18) The impact of Long COVID extends beyond physical health, significantly affecting mental health as well. Many patients experience anxiety, depression, and cognitive impairment, which can further hinder their daily functioning and quality of life. (21, 22) The functional impact of Long COVID is profound, with many individuals struggling to maintain their work and independent living due to debilitating symptoms. (19) Management of Long COVID often requires input from rehabilitation medicine experts, particularly for those with more severe or complex cases. While primary care may suffice for some patients, others may need specialized care to navigate

the multifaceted nature of their symptoms and to develop effective treatment plans. (18) Research into Long COVID is ongoing, with studies aiming to clarify its prevalence, symptomatology, and potential treatment options. The World Health Organization recognizes Long COVID as a legitimate condition, emphasizing the need for further investigation into its causes, which may include residual inflammation and organ damage following the initial viral infection. (23) As our understanding of Long COVID evolves, it is crucial to continue exploring its implications for public health and to develop comprehensive strategies for management and support for affected individuals.

CONCLUSION:

The COVID-19 pandemic, stemming from zoonotic transmission in Wuhan, has become a major global health crisis that highlights the need for international collaboration in health management. Progress in treatments and vaccination efforts, while significant, requires continued commitment to address challenges and enhance support for those affected by the virus and its long-term impacts.

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